

ISic1542

I.Sicily inscription 1542

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

alabaster

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Agrigentum

Place of origin (modern)

Agrigento

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἄγρ[---]λπικς
2. ἔζ[ησενἔτη] κ
3. [μῆνας] ια ἡμέ
4. [ρας---κο]δράτιλλα
5. [---]αλας ἐποί
6. [ησενμ]νήμης
7. [χ]άριϋ

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493895

EDR 136083

EDCS 41300013

PHI 175590

PHI 330042

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 26.1059i

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelika 6*. Palermo. At 1

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 35

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1542. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4354366>